

STORAGE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE ECO-SYSTEM

1st TNA Call Documentation - User

STORIES TNA POST RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE (WITH SATISFACTION SURVEY): USER (S)

General information about the project	
Project title (as used in application)	Energy storage in Seawater Batteries
Project acronym (max 15 characters)	SeaBatt
StoRIES TNA RI(s) accessed	KIT, Helmholtz-Institut Ulm (HIU)
Keywords (up to ten, free text)	Sodium; Seawater batteries; Bifunctional catalysts; Carbon current collectors.
Arrival date (in town where RI located)	01.03.2023
Departure date (from town where RI located)	31.05.2023
Starting date of access (first day at RI)	02.05.2023
Finishing date of access (last day at RI)	31.05.2023
Number of days not using the RI (during the above period)	31 days
Reason for not using RI those days (describe)	Weekends and holidays
Number of days using the RI	60 days
Number of users granted access (group size)	1
Comments	
Access Summary Report - work performed and initial results	
Brief description of the objectives of your project (up to 200 words)	
<p>The main goal of SeaBat project is development of low-cost, high-performance catalysts for seawater batteries (SBs) that promote oxygen and chlorine evolution reactions during charge and oxygen reduction reaction during discharge on their cathode side, i.e., in seawater. Focusing on high sustainability and environmental friendliness, which are the main advantages of SBs, the material has been designed considering not only performance but also cost and toxicity. Thus, our focus is placed on non-noble metal-based catalysts such as transition metal oxides (TMO) or layered double hydroxides (LDH).</p>	

Theoretically, oxygen evolution and reduction reactions of seawater take place at around 3.4 V vs Na/Na⁺. However, normal SBs with a carbon paper immersed in seawater show charge-discharge potential plateaus at 3.9 and 2.8 V vs Na/Na⁺, respectively, due to overpotential because of the sluggish kinetics of these reactions [ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces 2016, 8, 48, 32778]. In this project, we intend to improve the performance of a benchmark carbon-based electrode by applying catalysts and reduce overpotential during charge-discharge cycles of SBs.

Activities performed (up to 600 words)

Synthesis of LDH:

Synthesis of Ni_{1-x}Fe_x(OH)₂ was carried out according to the literature [ACS Catal. 2021, 11, 12, 6800]. Aqueous solutions of 0.4 M Ni(OAc)₂•4H₂O and 0.2 M Fe(NO₃)₃•9H₂O were prepared. 0.6 mL of the Ni solution, 0.24 mL of the Fe solution, and 6 mL dimethylformamide (DMF) were mixed and stirred for 2 hours. To this solution, 8 mL H₂O and 4 mL DMF were added, which was microwave-treated at 120 °C for 60 min and subsequently at 160 °C for 30 min. After centrifuging the sample at 6000 rpm for 5 minutes, the precipitate was collected and washed with ethanol. Washing and centrifugation were repeated three times. The purified sample was dried at 80 °C.

Loading of LDH on carbon felt:

Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) was chosen as a binder, which was dissolved in water at 90 °C. To 0.33 mL aqueous solution solubilising 2.5 mg PVA, 0.66 mL DMF and 5mg LDH were added and stirred over night at room temperature. 50 µl of the solution was casted on 0.25 cm² of a carbon felt.

Assembly of SBs:

The cells were assembled in a glove box and closed in a dry room. In the glove box, an electrolyte was prepared by dissolving 1M NaCF₃SO₃ in diethylene glycol dimethyl ether. In a bottom case of a coin cell, which was cathode side and thus has a NASICON (Na⁺ ion conductor) window, a Whatman[®]

GF/A grade disk with 17 mm diameter was placed and wet with 180 µl of the electrolyte. Then, a stainless steel anode current collector with a 12 mm diameter Na metal disc was placed. After placing a spring on the anode current collector to ensure the contact between the materials, a coin cell lid (anode side) was placed, and the entire cell was tightly sealed with parafilm. After transferring to the dry room and removing the parafilm, the lid of the coin cell was squeezed shut and sealed.

Set up of battery cycling test:

The closed cell was immersed into water to monitor possible failure during the cell closure. Once cell stability was confirmed, the cell was immersed in an artificially prepared seawater (0.47 M NaCl aqueous solution). On the cathode side, i.e., in seawater, a carbon felt (1 cm width and 4 cm length) with or without LDH was placed as a current collector. In addition to the LDH, another catalyst, which was supplied by a partner company, was also tested. The cells were connected to a galvanostat and cycled either at 0.1 mA cm⁻² for 1h for charge-/discharge (as a standard cycling test) or at 0.1, 0.2, 0.5, 1.0, and 2.0 mA cm⁻² for different durations to reach 1 mAh cm⁻² (as a rate capability test).

Scientific results (up to 800 words)

Synthesis and loading of LDH:

Ni_{1-x}Fe_x(OH)₂ was synthesised as explained in the former section. During the 1st synthesis, purification of LDH was carried out with water for two times and with ethanol for one time.

However, water partially dissolved $\text{Ni}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_x(\text{OH})_2$ and the yield was 5 %. For this reason, from the 2nd synthesis, solely ethanol was used for the purifications, and the yield was improved to 8 %. For the loading of catalyst on the carbon felt, two different binders were used: poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVdF) and PVA. The solvents were dimethyl carbonate (DMC) and water to dissolve these binders, respectively. When a droplet of LDH, PVdF, and DMC was casted on the $0.5 \text{ cm} \times 0.5 \text{ cm}$ area of the carbon felt, DMC quickly evaporated before the droplet seep into the entire area. Consequently, the LDH remained where the droplet was put and its loading was not homogeneous. For this reason, the combination of PVA and water was selected for the loading of LDH.

Cycling of SBs:

Assembled SBs were initially tested using the standard cycling test procedure, specifically 0.1 mA cm^{-2} for 1h charge and 1h discharge. In this procedure, the capacity of the cell is set to 1 mAh cm^{-2} , which is determined on a premise that Na metal anode will be replaced in the future by hard carbon anode (assumed theoretical capacity: 370 mAh g^{-1} and loading: 3 mg cm^{-2}) to improve safety of the system.

When the pristine carbon felt is used as the cathode current collector, voltage plateau was not achieved during cycling. After 10 hours of charging and discharging in the first cycle, cell voltages reached at 3.5 and 2.8 V vs Na/Na⁺, thus the potential gap (ΔV) was about 0.7 V. When the synthesised LDH was loaded on the carbon felt, the shape of the voltage profile remained almost the same. One barely distinguishable difference was that the cell voltage increased more slowly in the beginning of charging, and the charging voltage converges slightly lower than that of the cells with the carbon felts. However, this difference was observed only during the first charge, suggesting that the catalyst itself or its activity was lost during the 1st charge.

In contrast to the pristine carbon felt and one coated with the LDH, the cell with the catalysts provided by a partner in the collaboration exhibited a different behaviour. Specially, the voltage plateau was achieved during both charging and discharging, and the converged values were 3.2 and 3.0 V vs Na/Na⁺ (thus $\Delta V = 0.2$). Compared to the pristine carbon felt, ΔV for the catalyst-loaded

carbon felt was more than three times smaller. It is therefore possible to minimise overpotential of SBs by loading the appropriate catalyst on the cathode current collector (in the present case, carbon felt).

Interpretation of the results (up to 400 words)

Regarding the LDH synthesised during TNA, the reason of low catalytic activity is unclear. To assess the inherent catalytic activity of LDH, cyclic voltammetry using a rotating disk electrode should be performed and the results need to be compared to the particle size of the LDH. If the inherent catalytic activity is confirmed, the problem should be the procedure for loading LDH on the carbon felt.

For the catalyst provided from the company, the improved results are attributed to its electrocatalytic activity, which promotes oxygen evolution and reduction reactions. To confirm and discuss better about the effect of the catalyst, the cells were cycled also at different current density ($0.1, 0.2, 0.5, 1.0, \text{ and } 2.0 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$) to reach 1 mAh cm^{-2} . In this rate capability test, when the pristine carbon felt was used, ΔV varied from 0.72, 1.08, 1.78 to 2.52 V by changing the current density from 0.1 to 1.0 mA cm^{-2} . At the same current values, ΔV for the cell with the catalyst-loaded carbon felt were 0.31, 0.39, 0.58, and 1.42 V. The values are more or less halved by using the catalyst, confirming its positive effect.

The experiments were repeated at least 2 times to check reproducibility of the results. Although it was confirmed that the results were always improved by using the catalysts, the degree of the improvement was different depending on the cells. For example, none of the cell having the pristine carbon felt endured the cycling at 2.0 mA cm⁻² due to a huge overpotential exceeding set cell voltage limits. By using the catalyst, some cells were able to be cycled even at 2.0 mA cm⁻², while some cells were not. This is most probably due to the differences in the density of the NASICON separator, the degree of adhesion between the NASICON and the coin cell, and the accuracy of the cell closure. However, even including these experimental errors, there was clearly a significant improvement, demonstrating the positive effect of the catalyst.

Main achievements during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

The most significant achievement during the TNA work is the discovery of a useful catalyst for oxygen evolution and reduction reactions. The effect of the catalyst in terms of a reduced overpotential value was observed regardless the cycling current density. Because the catalyst was provided by the partner company, its exact composition is unknown. However, for sure, it was synthesised without precious metal such as Pt, Ru, and Ir. There are several literatures about catalysts for SBs, and most of them are based on Pt/C. Only one literature utilises the catalyst based on TMO [ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces 2016, 8, 48, 32778]. In this literature, the performance of SBs having TMO, Pt/C, Ir/C, and pristine carbon paper as the cathode current collector is summarized. When the cells are cycled at 0.01 mA cm⁻², the voltage gaps between charge and discharge were 0.58, 0.64, 0.73, and 1.05 V, respectively. The narrowest ΔV was 0.58 V for the TMO-loaded carbon paper. Although it is not possible compare directly this result and our results because the cycling speeds were different and ΔV for pristine carbon materials are different, the carbon felt containing our catalysts exhibited far narrower potential gap (0.2 V). This comparison confirms that the catalyst used in the project provides sufficient improvement.

Difficulties during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

When I visited HIU, all the necessary equipment was in operation. Because the institute is large, there were complicated procedures for new comers, including several safety training sessions and introductory training for each piece of equipment, which took more time than expected. However, I understand that these are necessary to organise a large-scale institute, which were good to know and experience.

Intended publications

I have obtained promising results that we can publish in the future. However, several experiments need to be performed to understand the improvement in SB performance with catalysts. In addition, I am currently carrying out cycling test of SBs by changing the limit of maximum capacity, which will take considerable amount of time (e.g., more than two weeks per cycle to reach a capacity of 20 mAh cm⁻² at 0.1 mA cm⁻²). As soon as these experiments are complete, I will prepare an article for submission to a peer-reviewed journal with a high impact factor.

Data management

The project is still ongoing. My supervisor and a student (KIT) are kindly helping me to take care the experiments and share the results.

Conclusions / additional comments

Our main goal of this project that is “development of low-cost and high-performing catalysts for seawater batteries” is achieved during the TNA, and further analyses which are necessary for future publication will be carried out in our laboratory at Sapienza University of Rome. In HIU, I have carried out a series of experiments that I was not able to do in our laboratories. I appreciate the support from StoRIES TNA project which allowed me to have precious experiences.

Did you complete the EC user questionnaire available at <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/RIsurveyUSERS> ? (necessary)

Yes No

Feedback – HSE, Ethics and Satisfaction

Please rate on a scale from 1 (excellent) to 5 (poor). Feel free to provide additional comments

Practical information on how to apply for Transnational Access and the overall application process	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

[Comment]

Information provided, once your project was accepted, on how to proceed	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

[Comment]

Support received at the site(s) regarding technical/scientific matters and logistics	Have you got sufficient support from the RI staff during the project? If not, please, specify the problems. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please specify any problems]</i>	

RI extension / upgrades required	In your opinion, is the RI needed to be upgraded? If yes, please give an explanation. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please specify]</i>	

Problems with local regulations	Have you had any problems with regulations of the visited RI owner (HSE, lab working hours, etc.)? If yes, please, specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No

<i>[Please specify]</i>	
Health and safety issues	Did you encounter any health or safety issue during your research? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environment & Ethics	Did your research deal with endangered fauna and/or flora and/or protected areas? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to humans, including research staff? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environment & Ethics – Dual use	Does your research have the potential for military applications? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environment & Ethics – Misuse	Does your research have the potential for malevolent /criminal/terrorist abuse? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environmental issues	Were any potentially dangerous substances (materials / gases etc.) released into the environment (atmosphere, water, or land)? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	

Ethics issues	Are there any other ethics issues that should be taken into consideration? Please specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					
Overall impression of communication and interaction after finishing your TNA related work	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>[Comment]</i>					
Suggestions for facilities not included in StoRIES which you would use for your research					
For the experiment of batteries, there were nothing missing. Some chemicals were missing, but the purchase procedure was very fast and was not problematic during my stay.					
Suggestions how StoRIES can improve future TNA programme, how to make the TNA more impactful on the energy storage technologies and how to enable the achievement of high TRL levels.					
I think making TNA more impactful is duty of users. For example, we have to participate in some conferences with logo and short description of StoRIES TNA project.					
Feedback – Pro-active Innovation Support					
Awareness	Did you know about the pro-active innovation support of StoRIES. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please specify how you learned about the pro-active innovation support]</i>					
Personal experience	Have you taken advantage of or benefited from the pro-active innovation support? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					
Information/service provided by the pro-active innovation support?	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					

I declare that the above provided information and especially that information on the number of days visited the RI is correct.

